

Klein-Gordon Equation and Wave Function for Free Particle in Rindler Space-Time

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Abstract: Klein-Gordon equation is a relativistic wave equation. It treats spinless particle. The wave function cannot use as a probability amplitude. We made Klein-Gordon equation in Rindler space-time. In this paper, we make free particle's wave function as the solution of Klein-Gordon equation in Rindler space-time.

Keywords: Wave Function; Free Particle; Klein-Gordon equation Rindler Space-time;

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1. INTRODUCTION

At first, Klein-Gordon equation is for free particle field ϕ in inertial frame.

$$\frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \phi = 0$$

m is free particle's mass (1)

If we write wave function as solution of Klein-Gordon equation for free particle,[3]

$$\phi = A_0 \exp i(\omega t - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{x})$$

A_0 is amplitude, ω is angular frequency, $k = |\vec{k}|$ is wave number (2)

Energy and momentum is in inertial frame,[3]

$$E = \hbar \omega, \vec{p} = \hbar \vec{k}$$
(3)

Hence, energy-momentum relation is[3]

$$E^2 = \hbar^2 \omega^2 = p^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4 = \hbar^2 k^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4$$
(4)

Or angular frequency- wave number relation is

$$\frac{\omega^2}{c^2} = k^2 + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2}$$
(5)

2. KLEIN-GORDON EQUATION AND WAVE FUNCTION FOR FREE PARTICLE FIELD IN RINDLER-SPACE-TIME

Rindler coordinates are

$$ct = \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0}{c} \xi^0\right), \quad x = \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0}{c} \xi^0\right) - \frac{c^2}{a_0}$$

$$y = \xi^2, z = \xi^3$$
(6)

We know Klein-Gordon equation in Rindler space-time.

Klein-Gordon equation is for free particle field ϕ_ξ in Rindler space-time,[1]

$$\frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi_\xi + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1)^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi_\xi}{(\partial \xi^0)^2} - \nabla_\xi^2 \phi_\xi - \frac{\partial \phi_\xi}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1)} = 0 \quad (7)$$

m is free particle's mass

For we write wave function as solution of Klein-Gordon equation for free particle in Rindler space-time, if we insert Eq(6) in Eq(2),[2,3]

$$\begin{aligned} \phi &= A_0 \exp i(\omega t - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{x}) \\ &= \phi_\xi = A_0 \exp i\left[\left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \left\{ \frac{\omega}{c} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - k_1 \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \right\} + k_1 \frac{c^2}{a_0} - k_2 \xi^2 - k_3 \xi^3 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Eq(8) is the solution's function of the wave equation, Eq(7) in Rindler space-time.

In this point, energy-momentum transformation is[2]

$$\begin{aligned} E &= \hbar \omega = E_\xi \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) + p_{\xi^1} c \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \\ &= \hbar \omega_\xi \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) + \hbar k_{\xi^1} c \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$p_x = \hbar k_1 = \frac{E_\xi}{c} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) + p_{\xi^1} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) = \hbar \frac{\omega_\xi}{c} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) + \hbar k_{\xi^1} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \quad (10)$$

$$p_y = \hbar k_2 = p_{\xi^2}, p_z = \hbar k_3 = p_{\xi^3} = \hbar k_{\xi^3} \quad (11)$$

In this time, we suppose $E_\xi = \hbar \omega_\xi, \vec{p}_\xi = \hbar \vec{k}_\xi$. In this careful point is we know $\omega, \vec{k}$ are constant.

But, in Eq(9),E(10), ω_ξ, k_{ξ^1} are variable functions with ξ^0 . Hence, $\omega_\xi = \omega_\xi(\xi^0), k_{\xi^1} = k_{\xi^1}(\xi^0)$

don't have to use in Eq(7),Eq(8). Energy-momentum relation is Rindler space-time,

$$E_\xi^2 - p_\xi^2 c^2 = \hbar^2 \omega_\xi^2 - \hbar^2 k_\xi^2 c^2 = m^2 c^4 = E^2 - p^2 c^2 = \hbar^2 \omega^2 - \hbar^2 k^2 c^2 \quad (12)$$

3. CONCLUSION

We found the wave function of Klein-Gordon's free particle in Rindler space-time. The wave function cannot use as a probability amplitude. In this paper, the particle has to do a spinless particle.

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